

THE RICH SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF MAHMUDKHOJA BEHBUDIY AND HIS ROLE AS A GUIDE IN THE JADID MOVEMENT

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***Abstract.** This article explores the rich scientific heritage of Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy and his pivotal role as a guiding figure in the Jadid movement. Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy made significant contributions to shaping the spiritual and moral values of youth, and many aspects of his legacy remain relevant today. As a champion of freedom, founder of the Jadid school, and an enlightened thinker who used theater and stage works to influence public consciousness, studying Behbudiy's scientific and educational activities has become one of the most pressing issues of our time.*

***Keywords:** jadid, jadid movement, prominent writer, public figure, publisher, new-method schools, modern education, state governance.*

A significant event in the political and social life of New Uzbekistan was the Presidential Decree No. PQ-462 issued by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on December 7, 2024, titled “On the Wide Celebration of the 150th Anniversary of the Birth of Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy – Founder of the Turkestan Jadid Movement, Prominent Writer, Public Figure, Publisher and Educator”.

The great legacy of Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy remains one of the most urgent and relevant topics today, especially for the heirs of the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan.

Behbudiy was born into a religious family in the village of Baxshitepa near Samarkand. His father, Behbudkhoja Solikhkhoja ogli, was a clergyman from Turkestan who served as an imam-khatib. In 1894, young Behbudiy lost his father and was raised under the care and supervision of his uncle, Qazi Muhammad Siddiq. He studied Arabic under Mulla Odil, another uncle. At the age of 18, he began working as a scribe in the qazi's office and, through his diligence, rose to the rank of qazi and later mufti.

During his pilgrimage (1899–1900), Behbudiy traveled through Arabia, Egypt, and Turkey. His experiences on this journey solidified his desire to establish a new-method (usuli

jadid) school. He opened such a school in the village of Halvoyi near Samarkand in cooperation with figures like Ajziy and Abdulqodir Shakuri in Rajabamin.

Between 1903 and 1904, Behbudiy visited Kazan and Ufa, where he familiarized himself with new-method schools and established connections with Tatar intellectuals. He began compiling textbooks for these schools, such as *Risola-i Asbob-i Savod* (“Book of Literacy Tools,” 1904), *Risola-i Jug‘rofiyai Umroniy* (“Introduction to Human Geography,” 1905), *Muntahab-i Jug‘rofiyai Umumiy* (“Concise General Geography,” 1906), *Kitobat ul-Atfol* (“Children’s Handwriting,” 1908), *Amaliyoti Islam* (“Islamic Practices,” 1908), and *Tarikhi Islam* (“History of Islam,” 1909) [1, p. 3].

Later, in 1908, Behbudiy transferred Shakuri’s school from Rajabamin to his own residence in Samarkand.

A major influence on the formation of young Behbudiy’s worldview was Ismail Bey Gaspirali, the founder of the Jadid movement in Russia. In 1893, Behbudiy succeeded in opening his first new-method school. In 1899–1900, he went on a pilgrimage. Through his efforts and initiative, new-method schools were established in the villages of Halvoyi and Rajabamin near Samarkand in 1903. Between 1904 and 1909, he authored educational materials for these schools, including *Risola-i Asbob-i Savod*, *Risola-i Jug‘rofiyai Umroniy*, *Risola-i Jug‘rofiyai Rusiy*, *Kitobat ul-Atfol*, *Amaliyoti Islam*, and *Muxtasar Tarikhi Islam* (“Abridged History of Islam”).

In 1903-1904, Behbudiy visited Moscow and St. Petersburg, and in 1906 he traveled to Kazan, Ufa, and Nizhny Novgorod. In particular, on August 23, 1906, he led the Turkestan delegation at a congress in Nizhny Novgorod dedicated to the problems of life and culture among Russian Muslims, where he delivered a major speech [2, p. 559].

In Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy’s socio-philosophical views, enlightenment ideas occupy a central place. He believed that only when knowledge and education were embraced by the broader public could they become a decisive force in social progress.

Behbudiy urged people to acquire the achievements of secular sciences, to adhere to the moral norms shaped by the social demands of the time, to cultivate humanistic ideals, and to become familiar with the teachings of Islam.

Behbudiy launched the publication of the newspaper *Samarqand*, which was printed in Uzbek and Tajik twice a week. However, after the release of 45 issues, publication ceased due to financial difficulties. On August 20 of the same year, he began publishing the journal *Oyna* («The Mirror»). This illustrated weekly was primarily in Uzbek, but also included poetry and

articles in Persian, as well as announcements in Russian. The journal was distributed across the Caucasus, Tatarstan, Iran, Afghanistan, India, and Turkey.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, under the influence of the First Russian Revolution, the enlightenment movement gained strength in Turkestan. As an educator, writer, dramatist, journalist, and legal scholar, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy stood at the forefront of this progressive socio-political movement. He consciously devoted all his strength, knowledge, and life to the struggle for the happiness of his people and homeland. After the Second Russian Revolution, Behbudiy considered it necessary to maintain unity with Central Russia and to support the direction led by the new working-class and peasant leadership.

Behbudiy also established a publishing house. He translated and published Fitrat's Bayonoti Sayyohi Hindi («Statement of an Indian Traveler») into Russian in 1913. On May 29, 1914, he undertook a second journey to Arab countries. During his travels, he visited cities such as Bayramali, Ashgabat, Krasnovodsk, Kislovodsk, Pyatigorsk, Zheleznovodsk, Rostov, and Odessa, and arrived in Istanbul on June 8. He then traveled to Adana and returned to Istanbul, where he met with Ismail Bey Gaspirali on June 20. Later, he visited Jerusalem, Beirut, Jaffa, Hebron, Port Said, and Damascus. His travel memoirs were published in Oyna, serving as a valuable and distinctive example of the early 20th-century traditional historical-memoir genre. In these writings, the author shared his impressions of the journey and highlighted the moral lessons drawn from his encounters. In every city he visited, he gathered information about its history, monuments, and notable historical figures. He took interest in the customs and cultural life of various nations and paid particular attention to issues of religion and belief.

The Oyna journal regularly published thought-provoking articles and discussions on the rights and history of the nation, language and literature issues, and the state of global affairs. Behbudiy believed that the progress of the nation required knowledge of multiple languages. In the very first issue of Oyna, he published an article titled “Not Two, But Four Languages Are Necessary”, in which he argued that one must know Uzbek, Tajik, Arabic, Russian, and even a foreign language such as French. At the same time, he published important and necessary articles about language preservation [3] and interlinguistic relations [4]. He paid great attention to literary criticism, trying to define its features and advocate for its equal standing among other literary genres [5]. He challenged opinions and views that undermined national dignity and demanded that the people of Turkestan be referred to by their proper name [6].

Behbudiy holds a special place in the history of Uzbek journalism as a prolific publicist. To date, about 300 of his articles have been identified, covering a wide range of topics. In his

early writings, he sharply rejected communist ideology, labeling it as “utopian” and “extremely harmful for us Muslims” [7]. He emphasized the importance of self-awareness: “Those who do not know the name of their tribe and their forefathers up to the seventh generation are called ‘marquq’ (disgraced)” [8].

Here are some notable acknowledgments:

“In terms of political and social activity, as well as the breadth of his knowledge, I believe that there was no jadid in Turkestan at the time who could rival him” (Fayzulla Khojayev).

“Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy deserves to hold the foremost place in the Uzbek literature of the national awakening period” (Hoji Muin ibn Shukrulla)ю

“A new literature has emerged in Turkestan. This was something I had anticipated... The center of this new literature in Turkestan appears to be Samarkand, and it must be acknowledged that the chief inspiration for the young writers is Mufti Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy from Samarkand” (Academician A.N.Samoylovich).

“It was Behbudiy and Fitrat who laid the foundation and initiated the development of Uzbek national literature” (Zarif Bashiriy).

These acknowledgments could be extended even further. His name was known throughout the political world—from the Emir of Bukhara to the General-Governor of Turkestan, and even to the last Russian Tsar, Nicholas II. He was highly regarded by prominent figures such as Ismail Bey Gasprinskiy, the recognized leader of the Jadid movement in Russia; Rizoiddin Fakhreddin, the editor of the well-known journal Shuro; Uzbek scholar Qazi Abdurashid from Siberia; and Sadri Maksudi, who lectured at the Sorbonne University.

The renowned Zaki Validi recalled with deep respect that Behbudiy’s speech at the First Congress of Turkestan Muslims in April 1917, held in Tashkent, redirected the thinking of the region’s intellectuals toward national independence.

Upon his treacherous execution, dozens of elegies (marsiya) were written. These elegies were not only expressions of recognition but also of sorrow and protest. They conveyed a sense of remorse - that the nation and homeland failed to appreciate and protect one of their greatest sons. They were also a protest by the children of the nation against the betrayal of the times.

This was in 1920. The Soviet regime, which had adopted the practice of eliminating the nation's most patriotic sons - those who truly represented the word Millat (Nation) - replaced sincerity with hypocrisy. It pretended to “mourn” with the people. Streets and schools were named after Behbudiy. Even the city of Qarshi, where he was executed, was named after him

for eleven years. Yet, in that same year - 1920, when Turkestan was mourning Behbudiy - another prominent jadid, Ubaydulla Asatillakhojayev (who had corresponded with Leo Tolstoy in 1909), was arrested in Moscow through denunciation and imprisoned in the notorious Butyrka prison.

Not long after, Munavvarqori served time in prison in Tashkent. In 1921, the case of Fitrat and a group of his associates was reviewed by the Central Committee of the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks), and following a direct order from Stalin, they were exiled from Bukhara.

In 1926 - the same year Qarshi still bore Behbudiy's name - Abdulla Qodiriy was arrested, and investigative files were prepared against Cho'ipon and Fitrat. In 1931, the first wave of political repression began. Behbudiy's name was mentioned less and less. By the infamous year of 1937, it was completely erased from public memory [1, p. 34].

However, he could not be erased from people's hearts. With the achievement of independence, Behbudiy was the first of our enlighteners to "come to mind". One reason he was among the first to be remembered is that the issues he raised were deeply connected to the fate of the homeland and the people, and to the very survival of our nation.

He emphasized that humanity is not an abstract concept, but a concrete one - it manifests in the form of nations. For each nation to be an equal and full member of the international community, it must develop and claim its rightful place through knowledge and enlightenment.

Behbudiy's entire activity and creative work were directed toward this goal.

Fate bestowed upon him the honor and responsibility of becoming the guide of the Jadid movement in Turkestan. When Ismail Bey Gasprinskiy first came to Samarkand and opened the first usuli jadid (new method) school, Behbudiy observed the forty-day teaching of Gasprinskiy's student, Majid Ghani-zade, and devoted himself to this mission. His 26-year activity - from 1893 until his tragic death in 1919 - stands as an unparalleled example of service to the Homeland and Nation.

First and foremost, Behbudiy was a teacher. He was both the theorist and practitioner behind the new schools in Turkestan. Through his intense intellectual and practical efforts, he rose to the level of a nation's teacher and became one of the spiritual leaders of Turkestan [1, p. 38].

Behbudiy was a great enlightener. Enlightenment is not simply the dissemination of science and knowledge, nor is an enlightener merely one who promotes them. History knows dozens, even hundreds of geniuses who mastered science yet ended up wasted like lightning

lost in the sky, or who destroyed fruitful lands like thunderbolts. Enlightenment is the light that science casts upon hearts. It is not a flame that burns, but a light that illuminates.

Behbudiy was a true patriot. He never set his nation against others; on the contrary, he was a broad-minded intellectual who regarded all the peoples of the world - including Russians and Europeans - with respect and affection. He believed that language, including European languages, was the key to science and knowledge. He advocated: “Not two, but four languages are necessary”. According to him, every Turkestanian must know, in addition to their mother tongue, Persian, Arabic, Russian, and even French; otherwise, one cannot live equally with the world.

He deeply felt the need for universities for the nation’s progress. He sincerely welcomed the opening of the Turkestan Muslim Darulfunun (university) in Tashkent in 1918. That same year, by establishing its branch in Samarkand, he made a significant contribution to the foundation of what is now our National University.

Behbudiy saw history as a powerful means of education. He sought national consciousness through historical awareness, and identity through a deep knowledge of history. He firmly upheld ancient traditions that connected us to the past. He wrote, “Those who do not know their tribe’s name or the names of their seven ancestors are called slaves or subjugated ones”. He held the honor of the nation above all else.

When colonial rulers avoided pronouncing the historically prestigious name of the people of Turkestan - calling them “Sarts” or “natives” (tuzemtsy) instead -he saw it as an insult. He initiated intense public debates in the press to defend the nation’s dignity, name, and honor. Despite official accusations of “sedition” and “political provocation” from N. Ostroumov, he risked his life by boldly demanding that the nation be called by its true name [9, p. 56].

Conclusion. The rich intellectual legacy left by Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy must today be studied not only from the perspective of the history of Uzbekistan but also within the broader context of world history. It is essential that the heirs of the Third Renaissance deeply understand the ideas of our great ancestor. For this reason, although a century has passed since Behbudiy’s death, his intellectual legacy has not lost its relevance and continues to serve as a living guide in modern education, governance, and religious spheres. He remains a contemporary and kindred spirit of our time.

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